

PRODUCTION AND USE OF CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS FROM TECHNOGENIC WASTE

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Annotation: This article reflects promising directions for obtaining new building materials using technogenic waste. The obtained results of the development of resource-saving technology for processing hazardous industrial waste from modeled in the form of flowcharts of technological processes for the production of construction products are reflected. Research has been carried out on the complex technology of mechano-chemical activation of waste from energy industry enterprises using phosphogypsum and red mud.

Key words: technological process, production of building materials, resource-saving development, technogenic waste.

Introduction. Among the wide variety of known technologies for the production of building materials using technogenic waste, there are no special prerogatives for the full-scale use of any of the building materials and products known at industrial enterprises [3, 4, 5]. This fact is explained by the need for preliminary preparation (cleaning, homogenization, drying, grinding and finishing, etc.) of the components of building mixtures associated with further processes of introducing additional operations and additional resources into existing production cycles, which significantly complicates the technological process and leads to the re-formation of harmful waste [1, 2, 6]. Thus, the task of developing and researching new effective resource-saving technologies for the use of man-made products in the manufacture of building materials is quite relevant.

The most common among the types of binding components of building mixtures is Portland cement and its modifications [7]. The specific gravity of this component in the composition of building mixtures is 35÷60% of their cost. The search and development of new effective binding components and their complexes are due to the following reasons: on the one hand, a significant amount of energy consumption in the production cycle and, as a consequence, the high cost of Portland cement; on the other hand, the need for new building materials characterized by a complex of general construction and special properties (thermal insulation, heat resistance, resistance to aggressive substances, radiation, biological organisms, with high or low density) [8].

Published materials on promising directions for solving strategic problems of the construction complex confirm the feasibility of using large-tonnage waste from the Vinnytsia region - phosphogypsum, fly ash, dispersed metal sludge and local natural raw materials in the technology for the production of effective building materials. The processing and use of such waste is beneficial from both an economic and environmental point of view, because at the same time there is a liberation of significant land from accumulated dumps of hazardous chemical waste and a reduction in the costs of their formation and maintenance [2].

The energy crisis requires the introduction of resource-saving technologies for the production of building materials. One of the effective components of construction mixtures is the ash and slag waste accumulated in the dumps of energy industry enterprises. It is also known that hazardous waste from chemical industry enterprises, in particular phosphogypsum, red mud and wastewater with a high acid content, have not been widely used in the building materials industry [3, 4].

It has been confirmed that one of the promising directions for solving complex national economic problems of reducing the cost of building materials by reducing the consumption of raw materials, fuel, energy and other resources is the expansion of the use of industrial waste as secondary raw materials. Such resource-efficient

raw materials, as confirmed by published developments, are associated with significant reserves for increasing production and its subsequent intensification [5]. Among the known technologies for the production of building materials using man-made waste, there are no comprehensive approaches to combining several varieties of man-made products in the technological cycle. The complexity of such processes is explained primarily by the need for preliminary preparation of the components of raw mixtures, since they differ in their physical and chemical properties. Existing technologies for using technogenic materials as components of building mixtures are associated with the need for their deep cleaning, heat treatment, the use of physical and mechanical processes of activation and changes in granulometry, which leads to an increase in the price of the final product [5].

The development of technological processes in sectors of the national economy and changes in consumer demands for construction products require the development of new building materials and, first of all, binders. The main components of building mixtures are cement, lime, gypsum, chalk, aggregates and chemical additives. The additives used in the manufacture of such mixtures are overwhelmingly imported to the Republic of Uzbekistan from abroad, and therefore their cost is quite significant. The resulting phosphogypsum-ash-cement binders based on chemical industry waste make it possible to solve the problem of energy and resource conservation, which is urgent for the Republic of Uzbekistan, by creating new multifunctional building materials [7].

According to sanitary and hygienic requirements, special attention is paid to building materials that are used indoors. The pretext for the full-scale use of industrial waste by manufacturers of building materials is the presence of natural radionuclides in their composition. Thus, the most promising area for the use of construction products with technogenic fillers will be the production of structural and thermal insulation materials for outdoor use.

The use of pre-activated fly ash as an effective filler in the composition of dispersion-filled concrete molding solutions is one of the promising ways to save

resources. The resource-saving complex method of mechano-chemical activation involves the destruction of the surface of the glassy shell of fly ash particles through the step-by-step use of acidic residues in phosphogypsum or its dissolution with alkaline solutions formed during the activation process with red mud. The use of activation processes for mechanical mixing of ash-sludge and ash-phospho-gypsum mixtures in a continuous mixer activator will contribute to a more complete destruction of the glassy shells of fly ash [8]. As a result of research, it was found that the activity of ash increases with increasing content of silicon-containing components in the composition of the filler compounds [4]. Destruction of the glassy shell by chemical activation provides access to the constituent components of the fly ash.

The implementation of the results of theoretical substantiations of the hypothesis of ash activation by acid residues included in phosphogypsum and alkali-containing compounds found in red mud involves the use of resource-saving technology for preliminary activation of components. In the process of partial dissolution of the glassy shell of ash, removal of acid residues and subsequent activation by alkali-containing compounds will ensure the intensification of the hydraulic activity of ash oxides [3, 6].

Conclusions.

1. The use of resource-saving technology for the production of building materials using man-made waste - fly ash, phosphogypsum and red mud in the composition of building mixtures allows us to obtain products of a dense structure with satisfactory physical and mechanical characteristics. The developed technology can, without the need for significant capital costs and organizational and technological measures, be adapted to the conditions of existing production facilities of enterprises in the building materials and products industry.
2. Conducted research into the complex technology of mechanochemical activation of waste from energy industry enterprises using phosphogypsum and red mud makes it possible to reduce the consumption of an expensive component (Portland cement)

in building mixtures by up to 35%, while obtaining an increase in mechanical characteristics.

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